

REACTION OF *cyclo*HEXANONEAZINE WITH DIENOPHILS

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Crisscross addition of *cyclohexanoneazine* and maleic anhydride has been studied with the formation of an adduct.

Azines though like typical dienes contain a conjugated system of double bonds, fail to undergo Diels-Alder reaction. In this connection reaction of benzalazine with maleic anhydride has been thoroughly studied. Snyder and co workers reported the formation of benzalmalein hydrazine (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 60, 2025). Wagner-Jauregg found that two molecules of maleic anhydride reacted with one molecule of benzalazine to give small yields of a product, to which he assigned the structure (I) (*Ber.*, 1930, 63, 3224). Van Alphen pointed out the possibility of structure (II) and favoured (I) on the following grounds (*Rec. trav. chim.*, 1942, 61, 892).

1. The compound cannot be benzoylated or acetylated and therefore contains no NH group.
2. The substance is stable towards reducing agents, while it might be expected that the hydrazine linkage would be opened in (II).
3. An intermediary product with one molecule of maleic anhydride cannot be isolated.

(I)

(II)

He subsequently showed that the crisscross addition of maleic anhydride to the azine system was a general reaction of aromatic aldzines, while this 1:3 addition failed with acetoneazine, acetophenoneazine and acetaldehydeazine (*ibid.*, 1942, 61, 895).

Recent investigations of Gartaro Coroma show that the nature of solvent plays a dominant role in the action of maleic anhydride with azines. In presence of the slightest trace of water maleic hydrazides (III) are formed, the amount of product increasing with the moisture content, up to a certain maximum. The course of reaction is reported to be as follows.

Snyder *et al.* had obtained benzalmaleinhydrazine by reacting benzalazine and maleic anhydride in moist ether and proposed similar course for the reaction (*loc.cit.*).

During our experiments with hydroaromatic ketazines, contrary to expectations, we observed that these azines very readily reacted with cyanic and thiocyanic acids to give crisscross adducts (*Cur. Sci.*, 1949, 18, 297). Our success with the above reagents prompted us to study the reaction further with maleic anhydride and other dienophils. We found that *cyclohexanonazine* reacted with maleic anhydride to give a variety of products, depending upon the conditions of reaction. In moist ether the reaction proceeds readily in cold, one molecule of ketazine reacting with maleic anhydride to give *cyclohexylidene-maleinhydrazine* (IV). The same product is obtained, in nearly quantitative yield, by reacting *cyclohexylidene-hydrazone* with maleic anhydride in absolute ether, but not so readily by reacting the ketazine with maleic anhydride in absolute ether or anhydrous benzene.

By refluxing one molecule of *cyclohexanoneazine* with two molecules of maleic anhydride in anhydrous benzene, toluene or xylene a different course of reaction is followed and besides a small amount of resin, the expected crisscross adduct 4 : 8-dicyclohexylidene-1 : 5-diazo-bicyclo- (0 : 1 : 5)-octane-2 : 3 : 6 : 7-tetracarboxic anhydride (V) is formed.

In moist ether, besides (IV), a small quantity of the 1:3:2:4 adduct (V) is also formed.

The resinous compound formed is insoluble in ether and benzene, but soluble in alcohol, from which it is obtained back as a viscous resinous mass, after evaporation. The properties of the resinous compound agree well with the salt-like addition product (VI), described by Van Alphen for Schiff's bases and azines with one molecule of maleic anhydride (*loc. cit.*). The resinous compound immediately decolorises Baeyer's reagent and bromine water and is split up by dilute sulphuric acid, *cyclohexanone* being one of the products. The quantity of resin increases if maleic anhydride and the azine are taken in molar proportions. In all our experiments small quantities of this resin were formed.

(VI)

Our observation of crisscross addition of maleic anhydride and *cyclohexanoneazine* are interesting as, so far we are aware, this is the first observed case of such addition with a ketazine. Van Alphen remarked that with the exception of the crisscross addition of benzalazine it was found that none of the groups: C=N-N=C, N=C-C=N or C=C-C=N are capable of adding maleic anhydride just like butadienes (*loc. cit.*, p. 895).

(VII)

Crisscross addition of α -naphthoquinone was next tried with the object of preparing polycyclic compounds like (VII). With benzalazine no reaction takes place in boiling anhydrous xylene. When fused together at 150° for 15 minutes, two compounds are formed, one greenish solid (decomp. 275°-280°) crystallising from glacial acetic acid, and

a tough brown resin, melting indistinctly at about 65°. With *cyclohexanoneazine* a small amount of a brown-black solid is formed on long boiling in xylene and exposure to atmosphere. The reaction is presumably preceded by the hydrolysis of the ketazine to hydrazone and subsequent reaction of the hydrazone with the quinone to give ketazine (VIII) or (IX).

(VIII)

(IX)

The view is supported by the reaction of *cyclohexylidene-hydrazone* with α -naphthoquinone in anhydrous xylene to give the same product (m.p. 305-307°). Quinones are known readily to react with hydrazones to give mixed ketazines (cf. Gerhardt, *Monatsch*, 1921, 42, 63). The product (VII) could not be formed. Hence, we conclude that *cyclohexanoneazine* reacts readily with maleic anhydride to give the crisscross adduct, while no such reaction takes place with α -naphthoquinone.

EXPERIMENTAL

cycloHexanoneazine.—To *cyclohexanone* (9.8 g.) was added 85% hydrazine hydrate (6 c.c.) with shaking. Heat was developed and the mixture became cloudy. The mixture was heated on a water-bath (90-95°) for one hour and kept overnight. On saturating with potassium hydroxide an oily layer separated. Fractional distillation gave *cyclohexanonehydrazone* (1.5 c.c.) at 90-92°/11 mm. and pure ketazine at 120°-122°/3-4 mm. Yield of the ketazine was 7.5 g., m.p. 33°.

cycloHexylidene-maleinhydrazine: (a) *From cycloHexanonehydrazone*.—Maleic anhydride (1 g.) was dissolved in 15 c.c. of absolute ether and *cyclohexanone hydrazone* (1.1 g.) was added. Immediately the solution warmed up and a yellow solid started crystallising and the mixture was kept for 3 hours at 25°. The separated crystals melted at 172° and the melting point was raised to 178° by washing with hot alcohol. The compound dissolves sparingly in absolute alcohol and crystals from alcohol shrink at 178° melting sharply at 180°, yield 1.4 g. (Found: N, 12.9. $C_{10}H_{14}O_2N_2$ requires N, 13.3 per cent).

The compound is insoluble in most of the organic solvents when cold. In warm dioxane the solution immediately decolorises Baeyer's reagent. In dilute alkali the compound readily dissolves, showing acidic properties. It is insoluble in cold water and gets hydrolysed by boiling water, maleic acid being liberated. The substance (0.1678 g.) on refluxing with 25 c.c. of distilled water for 2 hours requires 20.1 c.c. of 0.818 *N* sodium hydroxide solution.

(b) *From cycloHexanoneazine.*—To maleic anhydride (2 g.), dissolved in 25 c.c. of moist ether *cyclohexanoneazine* (2 g.) was added. The mixture assumed a pale yellow colour and became turbid within fifteen minutes; it was kept in a refrigerator for 16 hours. A pale yellow solid settled down. The ether layer was separated and the solid refluxed in absolute alcohol for half an hour. Major part was left undissolved as a yellow crystalline solid, m.p. 178-80°, yield 1.1 g. On washing with hot alcohol melting point became constant at 180° and there was no depression when mixed with *cyclohexylidene-maleinhydrazine* as prepared in (a).

Ether layer on evaporation left a viscous liquid which when triturated with hot alcohol gave a solid crystalline product (0.19 g.), m.p. 288°. Mixed melting point shows it to be the crisscross adduct (V). The viscous liquid also contains *cyclohexanone* (semicarbazone, m.p. 166°) and maleic acid (m.p. 129; showing no depression with a known sample).

4:8-Dicyclohexylidene-1:5-diazobicyclo-(0:1:5)-octane-2:3:6:7-tetracarboxylic Anhydride (V).—*cycloHexanoneazine* (2.8 g.), maleic anhydride (3 g.) and anhydrous sodium-dried benzene (25 c.c.) were refluxed on a water-bath. The solution gradually changed from pale yellow to orange-red and then a pinkish resin started separating. After a period of four hours quite a good amount of the resinous mass separated and benzene stopped refluxing. Absolute alcohol (25 c.c.) was added and the mixture further refluxed for 15 minutes. On filtering hot a greyish white solid was left, m.p. 285-87°, yield 2.6 g. On repeatedly washing with boiling alcohol the melting point rose to 290-91°. (Found: N, 6.9. $C_{20}H_{24}O_4N_2$ requires N, 7.22 per cent).

On evaporating the filtrate a yellow-brown resinous mass was left, insoluble in ether and benzene, but soluble in alcohol from which it was obtained in the same condition on evaporating off the solvent. Alcoholic solution decolorises Baeyer's reagent. It is partly soluble in hot water and the aqueous extract decolorises bromine water immediately and shows acidic reactions. The resin is vigorously decomposed by dilute sulphuric acid. All these reactions support structure (VI) (cf. Van Alphen, *loc. cit.*).

By refluxing *cyclohexanoneazine* (1 g.) and maleic anhydride (0.5 g.) in anhydrous benzene (10 c.c.) the main product was the resin, very small amount of the solid crisscross adduct (V) separating.